

Sensory and instrumental acceptance thresholds of pounded yam stretchability/extensibility

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Laurent ADINSI, UAC-FSA, Cotonou, Bénin

Laurenda HONFOZO, UAC-FSA, Cotonou, Bénin

Francis HOTEJNI, UAC-FSA, Cotonou, Bénin

Penelope PEDE, UAC-FSA, Cotonou, Bénin

Noël AKISSOE, UAC-FSA, Cotonou, Bénin

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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This document has been reviewed by	
<p>Oluwatoyin AYETIGBO, CIRAD</p> <p>Zoé DEUSCHER, CIRAD</p>	<p>05/02/2025</p> <p>14/02/2025</p>
Final validation by	
<p>Oluwatoyin AYETIGBO, CIRAD</p>	<p>14/02/2025</p>

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ABSTRACT

A main quality attribute of pounded yam is its extensibility/stretchability, with yams exhibiting high values being preferred by consumers. This study assessed the sensory and instrumental acceptance thresholds of stretchability through consumer testing, quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA), Kieffer dough extensibility and dynamic rheology analyses performed on twenty varieties in two experiments. Significant differences were evidenced among yam varieties for all studied parameters. Furthermore, stretchability was predicted by instrumental extensibility by Kieffer dough method ($R^2 = 0.61$) or $G'-G''$ crossover ($R^2 = 0.77$). A high stretchability is preferred by consumers, with the desirable sensory score above 8.01, on a 10 cm unstructured line scale, corresponding to biophysical targets values above 3.38 mm for kieffer dough extensibility (distance while stretching using texturometer) and below 1.52 kPa for $G'-G''$ crossover (using rheometer). Thus, Kieffer dough textural or dynamic rheology analyses are practically relevant in understanding the extensibility of pounded yam, and can be carried out to screen the various yam genotypes and determine textural thresholds for pounded yam extensibility.

Keywords: Kieffer Extensibility, $G'-G''$ crossover, screening, Consumer acceptability, yams, Thresholds

1 INTRODUCTION

Textural quality is a critical user-preferred quality trait for pounded yam acceptability by farmers, processors, and consumers (Otegbayo et al., 2021). Accordingly, the key textural attributes identified include hardness, cohesiveness, adhesiveness, stretchability, and smoothness, with stretchability being the major trait. Previous study established that the stretchability and hardness of pounded yam can be measured using a Kiffer dough test using a TAXT-PLUS texturometer (Adinsi et al. 2024b). In addition, the relation between sensory testing and instrumental extensibility was previously established while those linked to consumers' acceptance are not evidenced. Consequently, no acceptance threshold was highlighted for both sensory and instrumental measurements. Thus, JAR (just about right) and overall liking test need to be performed to fill this gap, so that the kieffer dough test can be used to readily identify preferred varieties.

Furthermore, Adinsi et al. (2024b) reported that among rheological parameters, $G'-G''$ crossover parameters from pounded yam were significantly correlated to stretchability scored by consumers. Similarly, Bolanle et al. (2024) reported that in situ rheological analysis of raw yam tubers is a potential phenotyping tool for quality evaluation. Textural and rheological analyses can be considered as medium-throughput phenotyping protocols and consequently are required for timely and cost-effective screening of quality traits in breeding yam germplasm. However, they can't be used to screen the varieties if the thresholds (acceptable range) of major quality traits and their corresponding textural and rheological measurements (instrumental) are not available. Thus, this study aimed to determine the thresholds of stretchability of pounded yam, and of the corresponding biophysical/instrumental variables.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Plant materials sampling

Plant materials comprised yam landraces obtained from Benin farmers' fields. They were used in two experiments (Table 1). For the experiment 1, they were collected in December 2023 as reported in deliverable of Adinsi et al. (2024b). Regarding experiment 2, they were harvested at September 2024 and comprised Agatou, Dodo, Efourou, Kokoro, Kratchi, Laboko, Monfobou and Ofegui varieties of *D. rotundata*, and Aga as *D. alata* species.

Table 1: Yam varieties tested for each experiment and analyses methods used

Experiment	Yam varieties	Harvest time	Analyses	Parameters used to predict sensory stretchability model
1	Aga, Agatou, Dodo, Efourou, Irindou, Kpete, Kokoro, Laboko, Ofegui and Wete	December 2023	QDA (stretchability, softness, sweetness), Kiffer dough test, dynamic rheology	Extensibility (mm), G'-G'' crossover (kPa) and G'-G'' crossover strain (%)
2	Aga Agatou, Dodo, Efourou, Kokoro, Kratchi, Laboko, Monfobou and Ofegui	September 2024	QDA (stretchability, softness, sweetness), JAR test (stretchability, softness, sweetness), Overall liking	JAR percentage_stretchability

2.2 Pounded yam preparation

Pounded yam was prepared according to standard procedure developed by Adinsi et al. (2024c).

2.3 Pounded yam characterization

2.3.1 Sensory analysis of pounded yam

Stretchability, softness and sweetness attributes were scored using the quantitative descriptive analysis, with 12 panelists for the both experiments. The panelists scored the randomly coded pounded yam samples for each sensory attribute in triplicate on an unstructured 10 cm line scale. The samples were served at around 50+2°C and the panellists immediately assessed the texture attributes for 2 to 3 min and, after that, the sweetness. Sensory evaluation took approximately 5 minutes, and three sensory sessions were performed for a sample.

2.3.2 Consumer testing

Overall liking data were collected from 102 consumers. In addition, the 3-point "just about right" (JAR) test (1 = Too weak; 2 = "JAR: just about right" and 3 = Too strong) was performed on stretchability, softness and sweetness

2.3.3 Texture analysis

Stretchability properties of pounded yam were determined by Texture Analyser TA.XT Plus (Stable Micro System Surrey, U.K.) coupled with Kieffer Extensibility Rig. Measurements were performed in ten replicates at 45 °C using load cell of 5 kg and following operating parameters: pre-test speed: 3 mm/s; test speed 2 mm/s; post-test speed 10 mm/s; distance: 40-mm; trigger force:auto-5 g. The parameters extensogram peak force (N), extensibility (mm) and extension area (energy, N.mm) were collected.

2.3.4 Rheological analysis

The rheological behaviour of the pounded yam sample was evaluated using a rheometer (HAAKE Viscotester iQ Air) equipped with parallel plates geometry with a ridged surface to avoid any sliding effect. The measurements were carried out at 30 °C and the temperature of the sample was controlled by means of Peltier effect system connected to a refrigerant (Viscotherm VT2, Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria). For each variety, three replicates were performed with 3-5 measurements per replicate. A subsample of 10 g was placed between the two plates and allowed to stand for 60 s before the measurements, while the excess of pounded yam was removed. Analysis was carried out at a constant frequency of 1 Hz, while strain amplification, varied between 0.1% and 1000%. The storage modulus (G' , a measure of elastic response) and loss modulus (G'' , a measure of viscous response) crossover and the corresponding strain were collected.

2.4 Statistical analysis

QDA and biophysical data were subjected to the analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the least significant difference (LSD)-Fisher post-hoc test (5% significance level). JAR test data were analysed by counting the percentage of respondents who evaluated each pounded yam sample as JAR 'just about right'. Linear (simple and multiple) regression was applied to predict stretchability by the biophysical parameters. The thresholds of stretchability and their equivalent biophysical parameters were determined according to method described by Bugaud et al. (2016) and modified by Adinsi et al. (2024a). All analyses were performed using XLSTAT (version 2016.02.28451, Addinsoft, Paris, France).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Sensory profile and consumer acceptability of pounded yam

Significant differences were highlighted among the landraces on the mean scores of stretchability, softness and sweetness of pounded yam prepared (experiment 2; Table 2). Monfobou and Laboko gave pounded yam of the highest scores (≥ 8) for stretchability and sweetness while the lowest scores of both attributes were attributed to Aga. The high value of softness was associated to Monfobou and Dodo whereas the hardest pounded yam were produced from Kokoro, Agatou and Kratchi. As far as experiment 1 is concerned, the sensory profiling of studied varieties was reported by Adinsi et al. (2024b). Consumers' overall liking of pounded derived from landraces varied in a great range; based on experiment 2, stretchability of pounded yam prepared from laboko and Aga were considered as JAR by 97.8 and 1.1% of consumers respectively (Table 2).

Table 2: Mean scores of sensory attributes and stretchability acceptability, of pounded yam

Yam varieties	Stretchability	Softness	Sweetness	% consumers scoring stretchability as JAR_ (%)
AGA	2.1 ^f	7.3 ^{bc}	4.7 ^d	1.1
AGATOU	5.8 ^{de}	6.8 ^c	7.4 ^{ab}	13
DODO	4.8 ^e	8.3 ^{ab}	5.8 ^{cd}	Nd
EFOUROU	7.3 ^{abc}	7.3 ^{bc}	7.8 ^{ab}	27.2
KOKORO	6.6 ^{bcd}	6.4 ^c	5.8 ^{cd}	65.2
KRATCHI	5.8 ^{cde}	6.7 ^c	6.9 ^{bc}	Nd
LABOKO	8.0 ^{ab}	7.1 ^{bc}	8.1 ^a	97.8
MONFOBOU	8.5 ^a	8.8 ^a	7.7 ^{ab}	Nd
MOROCCO	5.6 ^{de}	6.3 ^c	5.0 ^d	38.5
OFEGUI	5.9 ^{cde}	6.5 ^c	6.7 ^{bc}	50.5

Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$), nd: not determined

3.2 Textural and rheological profiles of pounded yam

All textural and rheological parameters exhibited significant differences in pounded yam samples (Table 3).

Table 3: Textural and rheological profiles of pounded yam

Products	Extensogram Peak force (N)	Extensibility (mm)	Extension Area (Energy) (N.s)	G'-G'' crossover (kPa)	G'-G'' crossover strain (%)
AGA	0.07 ^b	4.7 ^c	0.08 ^b	2.9 ^a	63.3 ^e

DODO	0.09 ^b	6.9 ^{bc}	0.14 ^b	1.9 ^{ab}	118.6 ^{de}
EFOUROU	0.16 ^{ab}	9.2 ^b	0.29 ^b	1.7 ^{ab}	280.9 ^c
IRINDOU	0.27 ^a	7.4 ^{bc}	0.34 ^{ab}	2.6 ^{ab}	244.9 ^c
KOKORO	0.22 ^{ab}	8.0 ^b	0.31 ^b	2.1 ^{ab}	246.1 ^c
KPETE	0.1 ^b	8 ^b	0.17 ^b	1.4 ^{ab}	199.6 ^{cd}
LABOKO	0.28 ^a	13 ^a	0.62 ^a	1.1 ^b	416.7 ^a
OFEGUI	0.24 ^{ab}	9 ^b	0.37 ^{ab}	1.8 ^{ab}	352.5 ^b
WETE	0.22 ^{ab}	7.2 ^{bc}	0.28 ^b	2.1 ^{ab}	253.1 ^c

Mean values with different superscript letters in the same column are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

Source: Adinsi et al. (2024b)

3.3 Relations between sensory attributes and textural and rheological profiles of pounded yam

Pearson correlation revealed significant correlation between sensory stretchability from QDA and the extensibility measured on texturometer (mm, $r = 0.78$) and then, with $G' - G''$ crossover (kPa, $r = -0.88$) and $G' - G''$ strain (% , $r = 0.70$) observed in oscillatory rheology. The results were already presented in the 2024 deliverable (Adinsi et al, 2024b) related to the relationship between sensory and instrumental stretchability of pounded yam ([doi.....](#)). These datasets were used to predict sensory stretchability.

The stretchability of pounded yam were predicted through extensibility and $G' - G''$ crossover parameters using stepwise linear regression (Table 4). $G' - G''$ crossover (kPa) and extensibility (mm) were considered as the first and second parameters, vice versa. When $G' - G''$ crossover is used as the first parameter in the model, F-test (0.23, $P > 0.1$, Table 4) suggests that the dynamic rheology analysis is sufficient to understand sensory stretchability. As second parameter, the F-test (4.76, $P > 0.1$) highlighted that $G' - G''$ crossover is relevant for the sensory stretchability model at significant level of 10%, but not significant at 5%. Thus, based on table 4, the parameters of the two types of analyses (texturometer or rheometer) do not enter the model simultaneously; it is not necessary to perform both analyses (textural and rheological), one is sufficient to predict sensory stretchability of pounded yam. This is a significant result that gives the freedom to carry out analyses depending on the

availability of equipment. (texturometer or rheometer) to screen the yam germplasm intended to pounding.

Table 4: Linear regression analysis for predicting sensory stretchability through instrumental parameters of pounded yam

Model	Parameter(s)	Model df	Residual df	Model SS	Residual SS	R ²	F-test value	P-value
1	G'-G'' crossover (kPa)	1	7	25.1	7.3	0.77		
2	G'-G'' crossover (kPa)+ Extensibility (mm)	2	6	25.4	7.0	0.78	0.24	> 0.1
1	Extensibility (mm)	1	7	19.8	12.6	0.61		
2	Extensibility (mm)+ G'-G'' crossover (kPa)	2	6	25.4	7.0	0.78	4.76	> 0.05 < 0.1

3.4 Sensory thresholds acceptance of stretchability of pounded yam

A strong linear relationship between sensory and JAR level (Figure 1) was highlighted with R² = 0.73. Based on the sensory analysis (0–10 cm scale), the optimal score was above 8.01 while the score is considered acceptable when it is higher than 6.72.

Figure 1: Relationship between sensory stretchability and JAR level

3.5 Instrumental thresholds for stretchability acceptance of pounded yam

The optimal stretchability (80% JAR) of pounded yam was characterised by extensibility above 3.38 mm or $G'-G''$ crossover below 1.52 kPa while the acceptable stretchability was associated to extensibility higher than 2.77 mm or $G'-G''$ crossover lower than 1.92 kPa (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Relationship between sensory stretchability and $G'-G''$ crossover (left) and extensibility (right)

4 CONCLUSION

Textural analysis or dynamic rheological is sufficient to understand the stretchability of pounded yam. Sensory and instrumental thresholds for stretchability of pounded yam was determined and can be used by breeders to screen germplasm. However, further study should be conducted to validate these thresholds.

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